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Research Article

**AN EXPERIMENTAL RESEARCH TO DESIGN AND IDENTIFY
THE EFFECTS OF LOW-DOSE UNITREXATE IN SECONDARY
SPINAL CORD INJURIES****Dr. Maryam Suryya Zafar, Dr. Rauha Ahmad, Dr. Safina Babar**
House Officer, Jinnah Hospital, Lahore.**Article Received:** February 2019**Accepted:** March 2019**Published:** April 2019**Abstract:**

Introduction: Various inflammatory and biochemical reactions may develop because of the SSCI (Secondary Spinal Cord Injury) effects which also known as secondary cord damage and it also creates oedema in the course of an acute stage.

Objective: Keeping in view the facts, the aim of this research was to design and identify the therapeutic effects of low-dose unitrexate for neuropathological disorders.

Material and methods: The design of this research was experimental in nature which was carried out at Mayo Hospital, Lahore (October 2017 to July 2018). We considered all the ethical protocols of the hospital in this research. The research sample consisted of one hundred patients who were suffering due to any of the neurological disorder and also used such drugs. The research was carried out in fragments by dividing the population into different groups.

Results: The varying mean MPO level values were significant according to T-Test and ANOVA. Treated group and control group were significantly different. Outcomes reflect that combined therapy of MO and MTX present closer values to the control group; whereas, a separate effect reflects different values than the control group.

Conclusion: We conclude that low-dose unitrexate is more effective than methylprednisolone to treat patients of neurological disorders.

Keywords: Low-dose, Neurological, Injury, Disorder, Myeloperoxidase (MPO), MP, MTX, SCI (Spinal Cord Injury) and Unitrexate.

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INTRODUCTION:

Various inflammatory and biochemical reactions may develop because of the SCI (Secondary Spinal Cord Injury) effects which also known as secondary cord damage and it also creates oedema in the course of an acute stage [1]. Such effect includes the release of aspartate and amino acid glutamate, arachidonic acid activation and glial cells activation. Microglial cells produce nitric oxide and superoxide in case of exposure to oxidative stress. Whereas, in the light of modern treatment the reduced cytokines production by the inflammatory cells blockage the secondary cord damage is also reduced [2]. At present, MP and low-dose unitrexate are used for the management of inflammatory diseases such as the damage of secondary spinal cord. Low-dose MTX inhibits lymphocytes proliferation for any of the response of inflammatory nature and reduces the leukocytes ability [3]. We still not know the exact mechanism of the drug but as per the available literature, it increases the accumulation of the adenosine at inflammatory sites. The interaction of Adenosine with receptors reduces the inflammatory cells [4].

The first standard drug for the management of SCI is MP for both human and animals [5]. A higher MP dose inhibits peroxidation of lipid. Present research efforts investigate the lipid peroxidation as it provides for the progressive tissue damage. MP also protects membrane against peroxidation of the lipid and it is a glucocorticoid steroid drug which also acts for other mechanisms along with peroxidation of the lipid [6]. Keeping in view the facts, the aim of this research was to design and identify the therapeutic effects of low-dose unitrexate for neuropathological disorders.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

The design of this research was experimental in nature which was carried out at Mayo Hospital, Lahore (October 2017 to July 2018). We considered all the

ethical protocols of the hospital in this research. The research sample consisted of one hundred patients who were suffering due to any of the neurological disorder and also used such drugs. The research was carried out in fragments by dividing the population in different groups respectively Group – A (Controls) and Group – B (MTX 30 mg/kg body weight) group.

Biochemical analysis was carried out through processing of blood sample through phosphate buffer saline with the help of homogenizer. Measurement of reactive substances was carried out through Mihara method [9, 10]. Suzuki method was employed to measure the blood sample MPO activity [12]. Blood homogenate centrifugation was carried out for ten minutes at a rate of (3000 rpm) followed by pallet suspension. Repeat the process of centrifugation for another five minutes at the same rpm rate. MPO activity was measured through separated resultant. Make a volume of one millilitre by combining phosphate buffer (50 mM), hexadecyltrimethylammonium bromide (0.5%) (HETAB), tetramethylbenzidine (1.6 mM) (TMB) and H_2O_2 (2 mM). Treat the reaction with H_2O_2 and measure the absorbance at (650 nm⁷).

The researcher also made a statistical analysis through T-Test, SPSS, ANOVA and PostHoc. Every outcome was shown in Mean and SD (P-Value < 0.08).

RESULTS:

The varying mean MPO level values were significant according to T-Test and ANOVA. Treated group and control group were significantly different. Outcomes reflect that combined therapy of MO and MTX present closer values to the control group; whereas, a separate effect reflects different values than the control group. Detailed outcomes of control, MTX and MP groups are given in Table – I & II:

Table – I: Mean LPO & MPO Values

Groups		Maximum	Minimum	Mean	±SD
Control	LPO	35.330	30.350	30.000	7.320
	MPO	0.010	0.000	0.000	1.570
MTX	LPO	58.630	54.300	54.300	7.460
	MPO	14.530	11.3600	12.500	0.840
MP	LPO	44.140	40.000	42.000	9.220

Table – II: Group-Wise Minimum, Maximum, Mean and SD values

Groups		Maximum	Minimum	Mean	±SD
MPO	MPO	5.320	4.850	3.250	5.200
High Dose MTX + MP	LPO	35.000	33.000	32.250	11.680
	MPO	64.140	60.140	62.140	6.140
MTX + High Dose MP	LPO	14.800	13.800	12.320	2.610
	MPO	38.000	36.330	35.320	0.640

DISCUSSION:

Various pharmacological agents describe protentional strong effects of the spinal cord injury. Another available treatment option is steroid therapy which is also accepted as the best available management for the spinal cord injuries. The effects are anti-inflammatory and antioxidant and they may favour while depending on dose and time [8]. They also carry activities like antiedema. We observed that every group presented degenerative actions except combined and control treatment groups. The inflammatory actions are also presented through histopathological grades along with cell degeneration in the specimen. These outcomes may also help in the explanation of MD and MTX response of inflammatory nature [9]. Furthermore, the MP group also presented a moderate inflammatory reaction due to neutrophils and inflammatory reaction of severe nature because of the macrophages in MTX specimen [10]. We may also say that MP is not capable to inhibit infiltration of the neutrophil into damaged tissue and low-dose of the MTX may increase histiocytic infiltration or macrophage into neural injured tissue in sub-acute SCI stage [11].

Macrophages and Neutrophils are best inflammatory reactions sources and they also free the radicals in any tissue. Moreover, SCI-induced ischemia faces the demands of the tissue energy and active ion channel functions after that it forces the neurons to shift from aerobic metabolism to anaerobic metabolism. This oxidative stress which is subsequent to SCI may also result in the production of free radicals that may initiate the activity of LPO in the neural damaged tissue [12].

Outcomes also reflect that low-dose MTX and MD also attribute in the free radical's formation and reduce oxidative stress as well [13]. When neutrophils and related phagocytes reach the spot of injured tissue of the spinal cord, they produce hypochlorite which is a strong oxidant enzyme synthesized MPO. MPO is an enzyme that is available in the neutrophils cells granules. The association of MPO activity is with the total neutrophils along with their activated state [14 – 15].

CONCLUSION:

We conclude that low-dose unitrexate is more effective than methylprednisolone to treat the patients of neurological disorders also known as secondary SCI (Spinal Cord Injury).

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